

Research article

Oronyms in northern Burma: Asymmetry between highland and lowland place names

KURABE, Keita

ILCAA, Tokyo University of Foreign Studies

Abstract: In Burma, which is home to around 130 languages, place names have a diverse set of etymologies. Although they are among the earliest evidence of human settlement and movement, there have been few discussions of place names in Burma, let alone northern Burma. This study, as a preliminary step in toponomastic studies in Burma, explores mountain names (oronyms) in northern Burma, where the Tibeto-Burman-speaking Kachin people and the Tai-speaking Shan people are among the major populations. For the present study, 484 oronyms were gathered and plotted on the map, showing the widespread distribution of Kachin oronyms in contrast to the marginal distribution of Shan oronyms. This situation is not parallel to the situation of the principal town names, where Shan place names prevail. This asymmetry could in part be due to the contrasting ecological settings occupied by the Kachins and Shans in northern Burma, with uplands on one side and lowlands on the other. One implication of this study is the possibility that not only the horizontal plane (longitude and latitude) but also the vertical direction (altitude) plays some role in the distributional pattern of place names in northern Burma.*

Keywords: Kachin; mountain names; oronyms; Shan; toponomastics

1. Introduction

Burma (Myanmar) is a multilingual country, home to around 130 languages (Glottolog 4.3) that belong to several major language families in and around the region: Sino-Tibetan (e.g., Burmese), Tai-Kadai (e.g., Shan), Austroasiatic (e.g., Palaung), Hmong-Mien (e.g., Mien), Austronesian (e.g., Moken), Dravidian (e.g., Tamil), and Indo-European (e.g., Bengali). Due to its ethnolinguistic diversity, place names (toponyms) in Burma present a diverse set of etymologies. Although place names are

KURABE, Keita. 2021. Oronyms in northern Burma: Asymmetry between highland and lowland place names. *Studies in Geolinguistics* 1: 1–15. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5529170>

* A part of this paper was presented at the First Meeting of the Geolinguistic Society of Japan, held at Aoyama Gakuin University, October 6, 2019. I would like to thank the two anonymous reviewers of this paper for their constructive comments. Any errors that remain are my own. This work was supported by JSPS KAKENHI Grant Numbers JP17H04523 and 18H03599, and the ILCAA joint research project “Studies in Asian and African Geolinguistics”.

among the earliest evidence of human settlement and movement, little research has been conducted on place names in Burma.

The same situation holds for northern Burma, which is mainly an upland area of hills and mountains encompassed within the mainland Southeast Asian upland area *Zomia* (Scott 2009), where populations are sparser and ethnolinguistically more diverse compared to the lowlands (Enfield and Comrie 2015). The Kachin and Shan (Tai) people are the two major populations in the region. The Kachins are linguistically diverse people who speak several distinct Tibeto-Burman languages such as Jinghpaw, Zaiwa, Lhaovo, Lacid, Ngochang, and Rawang. These languages are not always genetically close to each other. In this multilingual Kachin society, Jinghpaw serves as a lingua franca (Kurabe 2021). The Shan people are Tai-speaking. In northern Burma, they consist of several groups such as Tai Long, Tai Leng, and Tai Khamti, whose languages are very close.¹ Although the Kachins and Shans are close neighbors everywhere, the overall trend is that the Kachins are traditionally highlanders who occupy hills and mountains where they practice slash-and-burn agriculture. Their shifting cultivation causes greater population movement and limits the population size in each settlement unit. The Kachins were traditionally animists, but many have now converted to Christianity. Shans, on the other hand, are lowlanders in northern Burma who occupy river valleys where they practice rice cultivation in irrigated fields. Their wet rice cultivation allows consistent food surpluses and makes settlement units stable and larger. The Shans are Buddhists in religion (see Leach 1954).

(1) Major differences between the Kachin and the Shan

	Kachin	Shan
ecological	uplands	lowlands
cultivation	sifting	wet rice
settlement	mobile	stable
population size in each settlement unit	smaller	larger
language	diverse	uniform
religion	Animism	Buddhism

One toponomastic question here is whether the contrastive ecological settings of these groups are reflected in the distributional pattern of place names. This study, as a

¹ In this paper, Kachin varieties are collectively referred to as Kachin, and Shan varieties as Shan unless otherwise noted. When distinguished, Khamti refers to the language spoken by the Tai Khamti while Shan refers to the languages spoken by the Tai Long or Tai Leng. All varieties of Rawang are also collectively referred to as Rawang.

preliminary step in toponomastic studies in Burma, aims to address one aspect of this question, with a special focus on hill and mountain names (oronyms). This study shows that the Kachin oronyms exhibit a broader distribution in northern Burma, in contrast to the marginal distribution of Shan oronyms. This asymmetry could in part be due to the contrasting ecological settings occupied by the Kachins and Shans in northern Burma: uplands on one hand and lowlands on the other. Although preliminary, one implication of this study is the possibility that not only the horizontal plane (longitude and latitude) but also the vertical direction (altitude) plays some role in the distributional pattern of place names in northern Burma.

This paper is laid out as follows. Section 2 sets out to provide an overview of place names in northern Burma with a diverse set of etymologies. Section 3 is concerned with the data and methods used, followed by Section 4, which provides the results and a discussion of the pattern that emerges from our data. Section 5, as a supplementary note, offers a typology of Jinghpaw oronyms. Conclusions are given in Section 6.

2. Place names in northern Burma

Northern Burma is mainly occupied by Kachin State, the northernmost state of Burma, bordered by China to the north and east and the Sagaing Region and India to the west. Although Kachin State is an administrative division, its toponymy draws on a wide range of languages representing distinct strata. As noted above, it has long been home to the Kachin and Shan people, who are not always linguistically monolithic. It is also inhabited by some Nepali-speaking Gurkhas, many of whom migrated from Nepal during British rule in Burma. The Burmese population has also increased in size in recent years due to migration from Lower Burma. Due to its complex history and demography, the names of populated places there present a diverse set of etymologies. This is illustrated by place names in Kachin State with different toponymic etymologies given in (2). Because the Kachins are predominantly Christian today, there are also biblical toponyms, whose names are drawn from the Bible.

(2) Toponyms of Kachin State

Place name	Meaning	Etymology	Affiliation
Aye Zaydi	Cool pagoda	Burmese	Tibeto-Burman
Du Mare	Village of the chief	Jinghpaw	Tibeto-Burman
Yit Chyaw	Along the river	Lhaovo	Tibeto-Burman
Taqpeu	Upper village	Rawang	Tibeto-Burman

Mohnyin	Country of the spine	Shan	Tai-Kadai
Khamti Long	Great Khamti	Khamti	Tai-Kadai
Shatapru	Theta's city	Nepali	Indo-Aryan
Ziun	Zion	Hebrew	Semitic

Sawada (2011) explored the place names of Shan origin in Kachin State (mostly villages, towns, and cities, including four mountains) with a special focus on their etymologies, finding that nine out of eighteen principal towns in the four townships of Kachin State were named in Shan. This is in contrast to the five principal towns named in Kachin (three Jinghpaw, one Lhaovo, and one Lacid).² The following (3) presents the names of the principal towns in Kachin State with their etymology and meaning (reproduced and extended based on Sawada 2011).

(3) Names of the principal towns in Kachin State

Place name	District	Etymology	Meaning
Bhamo	Bhamo	Shan	Village of jars
Mansi	Bhamo	Shan	Village of cicadas
Momauk	Bhamo	Shan	Country that sends messengers
Mohnyin	Mohnyin	Shan	Land of the snipe
Hpakan	Mohnyin	Shan	Building up a wall
Mogaung	Mohnyin	Shan	Land of the drum
Waingmaw	Myitkyina	Shan	New town
Putao	Putao	Shan	Town an old man is looking at
Nogmung	Putao	Shan	Outside of the country
Injangyang	Myitkyina	Jinghpaw	Spirit altar field
Sumprabum	Putao	Jinghpaw	Jungle grass mountain
Machanbaw	Putao	Jinghpaw	Confluence of the Machan River
Shwegu	Bhamo	Burmese	Cave of gold
Myitkyina	Myitkyina	Burmese	By the big river
Chipwi	Myitkyina	Lacid	possibly Beeswax
Hsawlaw	Myitkyina	Lhaovo	possibly Hard to breathe
Kawnglangphu	Putao	Rawang	Konglang's village
Tanai	Myitkyina	Unknown	

² Place names in Lhaovo and Lacid are not always distinguishable because of their genetic proximity. Here the identification is based on the fact that Chipwi is mainly the settlement of Lacid speakers in contrast to Hsawlaw, where Lhaovo speakers are greater (Hideo Sawada, p.c., 2021).

3. Data and methods

A total of 484 mountain names in and around Kachin State were gathered from the GEOnet Names Server (GNS), the official repository of geographic names maintained by the National Geospatial-Intelligence Agency of the United States.³ The database includes around 5.5 million names outside the United States, including over 50 thousand place names in Burma. Associated information is also provided, such as geographic coordinates (longitude and latitude), the Feature Designation Code (see below), Primary Geopolitical Code (e.g., Burma), and Administrative Division Code (e.g., Kachin State). Our 484 mountain names were mostly taken from Kachin State, with additional data from neighboring regions in the Shan State of Burma, Yunnan Province of China, and Assam and Arunachal Pradesh of India. Oronyms were identified based on the Feature Designation Code: MT for a mountain, MTS for mountains, HLL for a hill, and HLLS for hills (Column L below).

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R
1	Words for Full name	Full name	Etymology	Unique Fc	Unique Ni	Latitude	Longitude	Latitude	Longitude	Military G	Feature D	Primary G	Primary A	Name Typ	Source		
2	Bum	Ndaung B	Ndaung B	Jinghpaw	-434558	-632338	27.07145	97.57694	27.04:17N	97:34:37E	47RLK588	HLL: Hill	Burma	Kachin St	Approved	NGA	GEOnet Names Server
3	Bum	Ngau Bur	Ngau Bur	Jinghpaw	-435005	-632849	26.77945	97.10462	26:46:46N	97:06:17E	47RLK115	MT: Mour	Burma	Kachin St	Approved	NGA	GEOnet Names Server
4	Bum	Ngrauju B	Ngrauju B	Jinghpaw	-435142	-633016	26.1753	97.13147	26:10:31N	97:07:53E	47RLJ132	MT: Mour	Burma	Kachin St	Approved	NGA	GEOnet Names Server
5	Bum	Nhkyen B	Nhkyen B	Jinghpaw	-435217	-633101	27.26667	97.76667	27:16:00N	97:46:00E	47RLL779	MT: Mour	Burma	Kachin St	Approved	NGA	GEOnet Names Server
6	Bum	Njaw Bur	Njaw Bur	Jinghpaw	-435328	-633219	26.21731	97.12624	26:13:02N	97:07:34E	47RLK128	MT: Mour	Burma	Kachin St	Approved	NGA	GEOnet Names Server
7	Bum	Nkang Bu	Nkang Bu	Jinghpaw	-435338	-633230	26.81546	97.93906	26:48:56N	97:56:21E	47RLK945	MT: Mour	Burma	Kachin St	Approved	NGA	GEOnet Names Server
8	Bum	Nkup Bur	Nkup Bur	Jinghpaw	-435351	-633243	26.54275	97.92819	26:32:34N	97:55:41E	47RLK932	HLL: Hill	Burma	Kachin St	Approved	NGA	GEOnet Names Server
9	Bum	Nweje Bui	Nweje Bui	Jinghpaw	-435587	-633516	25.35182	96.39927	25:21:07N	96:23:57E	47RKJ382	HLL: Hill	Burma	Kachin St	Approved	NGA	GEOnet Names Server
10	Bum	Abawm Bi	Abawm Bi	Jinghpaw	-409566	-604186	27.20761	98.0964	27:12:27N	98:05:47E	47RML10	MT: Mour	Burma	Kachin St	Approved	NGA	GEOnet Names Server
11	Razi	Agang Ra	Agang Ra	Rawang	-409599	-604225	27.25348	98.33091	27:15:13N	98:19:51E	47RML33	MT: Mour	Burma	Kachin St	Approved	NGA	GEOnet Names Server
12	Bum	Aikeng Bu	Aikeng Bu	Jinghpaw	-409647	-604276	25.64631	96.02182	25:38:47N	96:01:19E	47RKJ009	HLLS: Hill	Burma	Sagaing R	Approved	NGA	GEOnet Names Server
13	Madin	Ajeekawn	Ajeekawn	Jinghpaw	-409736	-604372	28	98.03333	28:00:00N	98:02:00E	47RML04	MTS: Mo	Burma	Kachin St	Approved	NGA	GEOnet Names Server
14	Bum	Arawm Pui	Arawm Pui	Jinghpaw	-410120	-604818	24.15011	97.39506	24:09:00N	97:23:42E	47RLG365	MT: Mour	Burma	Kachin St	Approved	NGA	GEOnet Names Server
15	Bum	Aru Bum	Aru Bum	Jinghpaw	-410123	-604821	26.17733	95.87465	26:10:38N	95:52:29E	46RGP87	MT: Mour	Burma	Sagaing R	Approved	NGA	GEOnet Names Server
16	Bum	Awk Bum	Awk Bum	Jinghpaw	-410468	-605209	25.61802	98.17573	25:37:05N	98:10:33E	47RMJ17	MT: Mour	Burma,China	Approved	NGA	GEOnet Names Server	
17	Razi	Azimatap	Azimatap	Rawang	-410523	-605276	27.4755	98.58409	27:28:32N	98:35:03E	47RML58	MT: Mour	Burma	Kachin St	Approved	NGA	GEOnet Names Server
18	Bum	Azor Bum	Azor Bum	Jinghpaw	-410527	-605281	26.79251	98.12097	26:47:33N	98:07:15E	47RMM12	MT: Mour	Burma	Kachin St	Approved	NGA	GEOnet Names Server
19	Madin	Bam Madi	Bam Madi	Jinghpaw	-410627	-605402	27.75958	97.31418	27:45:34N	97:18:51E	47RLL338	MT: Mour	Burma	Kachin St	Approved	NGA	GEOnet Names Server

Fig. 1 Dataset

In languages spoken in the Kachin region, oronyms are mostly expressed as compounds, typically consisting of the head (oronym generic) with a modifier (oronym specific) that gives more information about the head. For example, the Jinghpaw oronym *Lagat Bum* ‘Banyan mountain’ consists of a modifier *lagat* ‘banyan’ and a head *bum* ‘mountain’. In this study, oronyms were classified in terms of their head. This is represented by data in Column A above, which was added by the author. The etymology of the head provides a clue to the identity of a given oronym. For example, mountain names with the head *bum* are likely to be of Jinghpaw origin, while those with *taung* are likely to be of Burmese origin. This is represented by data in Column D

³ <https://geonames.nga.mil/gns/html/>

above, which was also added by the author. The following (4) provides a summary of the oronym generics that recurrently appear in our data, together with their phonemic/orthographic form, etymology, meaning, and example.

(4) Generics and their etymology

Generic	Phon.	Etymology	Meanings	Word order	Examples
bum	bùm	Jinghpaw	mountain	modifier-head	Nhkai Bum
kawng	kòŋ	Jinghpaw	hill	modifier-head	Hkada Kawng
madin	mədìn	Jinghpaw	wall/barrier	modifier-head	Lungkru Madin
razi	rvzì	Rawang	mountain	modifier-head	Ponggan Razi
hpawng	póng	Rawang	pile	modifier-head	Pagoi Hpawng
pam	pam ^F	Lhaovo	mountain	modifier-head	Lāngtsāng Pām
taung	tàun	Burmese	mountain	modifier-head	Saye Taung
shan	shān	Chinese	mountain	modifier-head	Fulu Shan
loi	lɔj ¹	Shan	mountain	head-modifier	Loi Maw
noi	nɔi ¹	Khamti	mountain	head-modifier	Noi Hkam

The order of the head and modifier varies across languages. As summarized in (4) above, the modifier precedes the head in Tibeto-Burman and Sinitic languages when both roots are nouns. By contrast, the reverse order holds for Tai languages (i.e., Shan and Khamti). Examples include:

(5) Order of the head and modifier

Jinghpaw	Kawa Bum	bamboo-mountain	‘Bamboo mountain’
Rawang	Damwang Razi	Damwang-mountain	‘Damwang’s mountain’
Shan	Loi Paw	mountain-father	‘Father mountain’
Khamti	Noi Hkam	mountain-gold	‘Golden mountain’

The spelling follows those used in the database, which provides spellings with and without diacritics (Columns B and C, above). Spellings sometimes do not follow the standard convention. For example, Jinghpaw *Chiran Bum* can be rendered as *Chyaran Bum* in the orthography. With our current knowledge, it is impossible to describe everything correctly. In order to avoid arbitrary decisions, we follow the spelling in the database unless otherwise noted. More examples from Jinghpaw oronyms follow:

(6) Variation in spelling

GNS spelling	Orthography	Meanings
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Weshi Pum	Woi Shi Bum	‘Mountain full of monkeys’
Njawhkü Bum	Njaw Hkri Bum	‘Topknot mountain’
Bautum Kawng	Bau Dum Kawng	‘Gong-sounding hill’

Each oronym was mapped on Google Maps. The geographic coordinate (i.e., longitude and latitude) of each location was obtained from the GNS database (Columns G to K, above), which provides geographic coordinates in various formats: Decimal Degrees (DD); Degrees, Minutes, and Seconds (DMS); and Military Grid Reference System (MGRS). Place names in the database are also uniquely identifiable based on the Unique Feature Identifier and Unique Name Identifier (Columns E and F above).

4. Results and discussion

Figure 2 provides 484 mountain names plotted on Google Maps classified in terms of the generics (i.e., the word meaning ‘hill’ and ‘mountain’).

Fig. 2 Kachin mountain name map (Kurabe and Sawada 2020)

Legends

	Loi	7	Mt.	Shan					
	Shan	7	Mt.	Chinese					
	Kawng	5	Hill	Jinghpaw					
	Hpawng	4	Pile	Rawang					
	Mahkü	2	Mt.	Unknown					
	Other	25							

The legend above shows the form of the generic element, together with its color, number of occurrences, meaning (where Mt. stands for “mountain”), and etymology.⁴ The map is available as Kurabe and Sawada (2020). By selecting a pin, its place name, longitude and latitude, and other relevant information are displayed, as shown on the left in Figure 2.

The overall trend shows a clustering together of the modern settlements of ethnolinguistic groups and the distribution of the oronyms. Jinghpaw oronyms are widely distributed in northern Burma. Mountains to the north tend to be named in Rawang, another Kachin group who have inhabited northernmost Burma and neighboring areas. Oronyms in Lhaovo, another Kachin group, are concentrated in the Sino-Burmese borderlands to the east. Khamti oronyms are located in and around Putao, and Shan oronyms to the south. Oronyms in Burmese, the speakers of which have recently migrated to northern Burma, are restricted to the southern part. Chinese oronyms are also restricted to the Sino-Burmese border.

What stands out in the map is the widespread distribution of the Kachin oronyms (around 400 mountain names). This situation is in contrast to that of the Shan oronyms, which show a marginal distribution (around 20 mountain names). This is summarized below.

(7) Kachin and Shan oronyms

Bum	335	Jinghpaw	Kachin
Madin	21	Jinghpaw	Kachin
Kawng	5	Jinghpaw	Kachin
Razi	44	Rawang	Kachin
Hpawng	4	Rawang	Kachin
Pam	9	Lhaovo	Kachin
Noi	12	Khamti	Shan

⁴ A reviewer suggested the possibility that the oronym generic *mahkü* could have a connection with /khu/ ‘mountain’ in some Lisu dialects.

Loi 7 Shan Shan

This distributional asymmetry is in part due to the fact that the Kachin population is greater than the Shan in modern northern Burma although the Shans were the dominant group there for a long time. In the 1983 Census, the ethnic composition in Kachin State was: Kachin (38.1%), Shan (24.2%), and Burmese (29.3%). The asymmetry becomes even clearer when contrasted with the distribution of the principal town names (see §2), where Shan place names prevail: nine out of eighteen are in Shan while five are in Kachin (three Jinghpaw, one Lhaovo, and one Lacid). Although more research is required, the asymmetry found in the oronyms could in part be attributed to the contrastive ecological setting of the Kachins and Shans in northern Burma: uplands on one hand and lowlands on the other. The remote uplands would have been beyond the reach of the influential lowlanders. It should also be noted that the principal towns in Shan are mostly located in lowlands in contrast to those in Kachin, which tend to be located on relatively high grounds. While preliminary, one implication of the distribution of the oronyms, coupled with that of principal town names, is the possibility that not only the horizontal plane (longitude and latitude) but also the vertical direction (altitude) plays some role in the distributional pattern of place names in northern Burma. This echoes the observation made by the geographer and historian Paul Wheatley regarding India that “the Sanskrit tongue was chilled to silence at 500 meters” (Wheatley 1975: 251).

The large body of oronyms in the region also shows that hills and mountains are not trivial for upland peoples. It can generally be observed that mountains tend to be named relatively late because of their economic marginality (Drummond 2016). This would not always be the case when considering highlanders like the Kachin, whose lives are directly connected to the hills and mountains.

The contrast between upland and lowland areas in northern Burma is also reflected in the lexico-grammatical domain. For example, many Kachin languages have height-based demonstratives that are sensitive to the relative height of the referent. This is illustrated by distal demonstratives below (adapted from Kurabe 2021). By contrast, height-based demonstratives are alien to Shan.

(8) Height-based distal demonstratives

	Jinghpaw	Zaiwa	Lhaovo	Lacid	Leqi	Ngochang
Distal (up)	thó	hu ³¹	tho ^L	fu:	xu ³³	thyih
Distal (level)	wó	hye ³¹	thø ^L	thi:	thə ³³	thyi-mha
Distal (down)	lé	mvo ³¹	mø ^L	mɔ:	mɔ̃ ³³	mhoh

The Kachin languages of the Burmish group have also developed a set of deictic motion verbs that are sensitive to relative height. Examples are given below (Lustig 2010, Sawada 2004, Hkaw Luk 2017, Dai 2007, Yabu 1990, respectively). By contrast, Shan languages only distinguish between ‘to come’ and ‘to go’.

(9) Deictic motion verbs

	Zaiwa	Lhaovo	Lacid	Leqi	Ngochang
come down	lye ³⁵	li ^H	ɿé	le: ⁵⁵	lí
come up	lo ³¹	lo ^F	lɔ	lo: ⁵³	lô
go down	ye ³¹	ye ^L	ji:	je: ³³	ʔe
go up	lo ³⁵	lo ^H	lɔ	lo: ⁵⁵	ló

The contrast is also reflected in personal pronoun systems. The highland languages of mainland Southeast Asia tend to have a simple personal pronoun system in contrast to lowlands languages with hierarchically stratified societies, which tend to exhibit more complex system (Müller and Weymuth 2017). The Kachin personal pronoun system is relatively simple with no distinctions involving age, gender, or politeness. By contrast, Shan languages often encode more elaborated distinctions such as politeness.

5. Typology of Jinghpaw oronyms

This section, as a supplementary note, provides a brief typology of mountain names in Jinghpaw. Jinghpaw mountain names were first identified based on the generic element (e.g., *bum* ‘mountain’). The meanings of the specific element were then identified with the help of a Jinghpaw consultant in the course of two separate fieldworks in Myitkyina, Kachin State, between January and March 2019. When classified in terms of the specific element, recurrent categories that emerged from our data can be summarized as follows.⁵

(10) Jinghpaw oronym classification

Types	Examples	Meanings
Kinship	Nhkai Bum	‘Nhkai lineage’s mountain’
Biological	Lagat Bum	‘Banyan mountain’
Topographical	Hkama Hku Bum	‘Mountain upstream of the Hkama River’

⁵ The spelling of mountain names in this section follows the convention of the Jinghpaw orthography.

Geological	Kagam Bum	‘Clay mountain’
Mythological	Bau Dum Bum	‘Gong-sounding mountain’
Metaphorical	Sam Ngam Bum	‘Full-grown mountain’

Of these, the most common are oronyms based on kinship. These oronyms include clan (*amyu*) names or lineage (*ru sai*) names as their specifics. Oronyms based on given names, by contrast, are almost absent. Clans and lineages are integral to Kachin society. The Kachin clans go beyond internal-linguistic boundaries; they are divided into major lineages, which in turn are further divided into minor segments and local lineage groups. In the major chiefdoms, the majority of the residents belong to the clan of the chief who owns the village land (see Hanson 1913, Lehman 1993). Due to this situation, it is not unlikely for mountains belonging to the land of a clan or lineage to be named after the settler. Further examples illustrating this category in our data are the following:

(11) Kinship-based oronyms

Abawm Bum	Yudam Bum	Sut Jawn Bum
Malang Bum	Punlum Bum	Bawnggan Bum
Ndawng Bum	Htaya Bum	Bumrawng Bum
Saupan Bum	Ndap Bum	Hpaungma Bum
Tawai Bum	Lasi Bum	Shanghkawng Bum
Pali Bum	Shadau Bum	La-awng Bum
Lakeng Bum	Htangde Bum	N-gau Hkang Bum
Walaw Bum	Lakeng Bum	Mawchyi Bum
Hpaukan Bum	Gumtung Bum	Shanghkawng Bum
Tawai Bum	Kumreng Bum	Hkabawng Kawng

Another common category consists of oronyms named based on the biological characteristics of mountains. These include oronyms with specific elements that include plant and animal names. For example, oronyms named in faunal terms include *Lagat Bum*, which literally means ‘Banyan mountain’. Other examples include:

(12) Plant-based oronyms

Chyaran Bum	‘Chestnut mountain’
Bying Bum	‘Cherry mountain’
Kawa Bum	‘Bamboo mountain’
Nai Ru Bum	‘Yam vine mountain’
Sumpra Bum	‘Jungle grass mountain’

Kumba Bum	‘Elephant grass mountain’
Wuraw Bum	‘Spiny bamboo mountain’
Lagyep Bum	‘Wild plantain mountain’
Panteng Bum	‘Variegated flower mountain’
Hpalai Bum	‘Hpalai leaf mountain’
Kindu Bum	‘Kindu grass mountain’
Hkying Bum	‘Ginger mountain’
Tangau Bum	‘Rattan mountain’

Oronym nomenclature in Jinghpaw also exhibits a set of oronyms named in relation to animals. These include mountains named after animals that inhabit the area (e.g., ‘Deer mountain’ below) and those named after animals that have some relationship to the place (e.g., ‘Mountain that dogs long for’ below).

(13) Animal-based oronyms

Shat Nga Bum	‘Deer mountain’
Galang Kri Bum	‘Eagle-spinning mountain’
Ninggrau Ju Bum	‘White-handed gibbon mountain’
U Jat Bum	‘Mountain full of birds’
U Zwi Bum	‘U Zwi bird mountain’
Magwi Bum	‘Elephant mountain’
Woi Chyai Bum	‘Monkey-playing mountain’
Gwi Marit Bum	‘Mountain that dogs long for’

The next common category is characterized by mountains that are named in terms of their topographical features. For example, *Hkama Hku Bum* ‘Mountain upstream of the Hkama River’ is named after the topographical landmark to which it is related, *Hpung Wai Bum* ‘Mountain surrounded by the river’ is named based on its topographical characteristics, and *Tingsen Bum* ‘Pointed mountain’ is named based on its shape. Further examples include:

(14) Topographical

Matsi Hku Bum	‘Mountain upstream of the Matsi River’
Wurat Hku Bum	‘Mountain upstream of the Wurats River’
Lagat Hku Bum	‘Mountain upstream of the Lagat River’
Hka Yat Bum	‘Mountain where the river falls’
Lang Nem Bum	‘Straight and low mountain’

Hkrau Bum	‘Spreading mountain’
Bum Pa Bum	‘Flat mountain’
Bum Lang Bum	‘Straight mountain’
Hpun Hpu Bum	‘Swollen mountain’

Metaphors also play a role in the mountain name nomenclature. For example, the oronym ‘Flea mountain’ below contains *wa salang* ‘flea’ as its specific element because the mountain is said to be as small as a flea. The name ‘Cradle mountain’ is based on the similarity to a cradle in form. Toponymic metaphors are also illustrated by personification. The mountain ‘Full-grown mountain’ is viewed as a full-grown man (*wa ngan*). A similar metaphorical pathway is reflected in the names ‘Old woman mountain’ and ‘Bald mountain’. The oronym ‘Cheating mountain’ gets its name from the fact that the mountain often leads people astray.

(15) Metaphorical

Wa Salang Bum	‘Flea mountain’
Singgoi Bum	‘Cradle mountain’
Gumgai Bum	‘Old woman mountain’
Wa Ngan Tan Bum	‘Full-grown mountain’
Bum Krin Bum	‘Bald mountain’
Lem Hpa Bum	‘Cheating mountain’

Mountains are sometimes named with reference to their geological features. For example, *Kagam Bum* ‘Clay mountain’ and *Bum Pat Bum* ‘Amber mountain’ carry the name of the soil and mineral as their specifics. The oronym *Bau Dum Bum* ‘Gong-sounding mountain’ is named based on the local belief that spirits (or *nats*) beat the gong in the mountain when people die. Mountains with good views and sunshine are named *Mada Bum* ‘Observatory mountain’ and *Jan Mai Bum* ‘Sunny mountain’, respectively.

6. Conclusions

This paper explored toponomastics in northern Burma, with a special focus on oronyms based on more than 480 hill and mountain names. One of the significant findings to emerge from our data is the widespread distribution of Kachin oronyms (ca. 400 mountain names), which contrasts with the marginal distribution of Shan oronyms

(ca. 20 mountain names). This situation is not the same as that of the principal town names, in which Shan place names prevail. Although more detailed investigations are required, this asymmetry could in part be due to the contrasting ecological settings occupied by the Kachins and Shans in northern Burma: uplands on one hand and lowlands on the other. While preliminary, our data could contribute to a better understanding of the distributional patterns of place names in mountainous areas: the role played not only by the horizontal plane (longitude and latitude) but also the vertical direction (altitude). This paper also showed that many mountains have their own names in northern Burma. The large body of oronyms in the area suggests that hills and mountains are not trivial features of the landscape to highlanders like the Kachins, whose lives are directly connected to the uplands where they dwell and earn their livelihoods.

The question raised in this study should be further explored in consideration of different types of geographical features, both natural and cultural (human-made). Further work on populated place names (e.g., villages) is especially important because they are both comparable and numerous. However, this is not an easy task. For one thing, the identification of the etymology of populated place names is much more difficult, since the generic (e.g., the element meaning the village) is often missing from the database. For another thing, the GNS database does not provide information about the altitude of populated place names in northern Burma. The scope of this study is admittedly limited because the etymology of the oronyms is mostly identified based on generic elements. A closer look at the specific elements is equally necessary to develop a more complete picture. Another limitation stems from the nature of the database; in some cases, more than one name may be attached to a single mountain – for example, one in Kachin and another in Shan. It is thus important to identify from which point of view the place names were recorded. Such information cannot be extractable from the database. If this debate is to be moved forward, a better understanding of folk etymology must also be developed.

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Publication history

Date received: 28 April 2021

Date accepted: 23 June 2021